

ON CRITTENDEN AND VANDEN EYNDEN'S CONJECTURE

FLORENTIN SMARANDACHE

It is possible to cover all (positive) integers with n geometrical progressions of integers?

Find a necessary and sufficient condition for a general class of positive integer sequences such that, for a fixed n , there are n (distinct) sequences of this class which cover all integers.

Comments:

a) No. Let a_1, \dots, a_n be respectively the first terms of each geometrical progression, and q_1, \dots, q_n respectively their ratios. Let p be a prime number different from $a_1, \dots, a_n, q_1, \dots, q_n$. Then p does not belong to the union of these n geometrical progressions.

b) For example, the class of progressions

$A_f = \left\{ \{a_n\}_{n \geq 1} : a_n = f(a_{n-1}, \dots, a_{n-i}) \text{ for } n \geq i+1, \text{ and } i, a_1, a_2, \dots \in N^* \right\}$ with the property

$\exists y \in N^*, \forall (x_1, \dots, x_i) \in N^{*i} : f(x_1, \dots, x_i) \neq y$. Does it cover all integers?

But, if $\forall y \in N^*, \exists (x_1, \dots, x_i) \in N^{*i} : f(x_1, \dots, x_i) = y$?

(Generally no.)

This (solved and unsolved) problem remembers Crittenden and Vanden Eynden's conjecture.

References:

- [1] R.B. Crittenden and C. L. Vanden Eynden, *Any n arithmetic progressions covering the first 2^n integers covers all integers*, Proc. Amer. Math. Soc. 24 (1970) 475-481.
- [2] R.B. Crittenden and C. L. Vanden Eynden, *The union of arithmetic progression with differences not less than k* , Amer. Math. Monthly 79 (1972) 630.
- [3] R. K. Guy, *Unsolved Problem in Number Theory*, Springer-Verlag, New York, Heidelberg, Berlin, 1981, Problem E23, p.136.